

DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICES AS A FACTOR IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A LOGISTIC ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the issues of organizing and developing logistics services in an organization. A definition of logistics service is given, and the main groups in the field of logistics services are considered. The degree of influence of logistics services on the competitiveness of an organization is analyzed. The criteria for service quality that influence the attitude of consumers towards the organization are determined.

Keywords: Logistics, service, logistic services, customer satisfaction, competitive advantages.

In connection with the transition from a seller's market to a buyer's market, firms have increasingly focused on increasing their competitiveness. One of the factors that increases the competitiveness of a company is the construction of an effective logistics system. Each company is a complex mechanism with its own characteristics, goals and means. Moreover, when building a system for effective functioning in the market, it is necessary to take into account many different factors.

Logistics allows you to significantly reduce the time interval between the purchase of raw materials and semi-finished products and the delivery of the finished product to the consumer, contributes to a sharp reduction in material inventories, speeds up the process of obtaining information, and increases the level of service [1].

Currently, there are rarely companies on the market that provide their consumers only with goods or provide only services in their pure form. To sell a product, it is necessary to give it properties that meet the needs of the buyer and distinguish it from competitors. Research shows that attracting new consumers costs a company more than retaining existing ones, so modern companies focus their efforts on maintaining consumer loyalty, using various measures, including the development of logistics services, expanding the scope of services provided, and improving the quality of service.

Providing a range of services in the process of purchasing and selling involves bringing the purchased goods to consumers. Moreover, the more different services are provided, the higher the use value of the product will be. This is aimed at modifying the product offer, without which modern trade cannot function successfully in a competitive market. All this predetermines the successful development of various types of services.

Logistics service can be understood as a set of intangible logistics operations that ensure maximum satisfaction of consumer demand in the process of managing material and information flows in the most optimal way, from a cost point of view.

All work in the field of logistics services can be divided into three main groups:

- Pre-sales, i.e. work on the formation of a logistics service system;
- Work on the provision of logistics services carried out in the process of selling goods;
- After-sales logistics service.

Before the implementation process begins, work in the field of logistics services mainly includes determining the company's policy in the provision of services, as well as their planning.

In the process of selling goods, a variety of logistics services can be provided, for example:

- Availability of inventory in the warehouse;
- order execution, including assortment selection, packaging, formation of cargo units and other operations;
- ensuring delivery reliability;
- providing information on the passage of goods.

After-sales services include warranty service, obligations to address customer complaints, and exchanges [2].

In modern market conditions, the buyer influences the success of the seller. Buyers are becoming more and more demanding and professional, they are looking for goods and services adapted to their characteristics, and are seeking completeness of purchasing information. Today, purchasing decisions have become more prepared. A characteristic feature was the emergence of a "connoisseur buyer" with the following qualities:

- High awareness of products of interest and the ability to compare and choose distracted from advertising, brands or sellers. This means the ability to find the best quality/price ratio.

- The ability to separate the properties of the goods themselves from the services at the point of sale that increase the value of the goods. Thus, the connoisseur usually compares the quality not only of the goods themselves, which can be purchased anywhere, but also of the stores.

- Ability to quickly recognize almost identical brands. A connoisseur will not necessarily choose a well-known brand over a lesser-known one simply because it is more familiar to him or because of its image. A product should always be perceived as having special value.

Thus, in order to be accepted by the market, a company needs to satisfy consumer demand, which is not always limited to demand for the product itself. To maintain competitiveness, the company needs to develop measures for the organization and development of logistics services [3].

Planning a logistics service includes: determining a list of services that are significant for the buyer, ranking services, determining service standards, determining the optimal level of service.

To assess the quality of service, it is necessary to monitor consumer satisfaction with the quality of service, since improving the quality of logistics services is closely related to the successful conduct of the company's business as a whole.

To monitor customer satisfaction with the level of logistics services, it is necessary to determine service quality criteria. The criteria for measuring service quality are:

- Tangibility (appearance of the staff, convenience of the office location, availability of a convenient approach and access to the place where the service is provided, agreed upon time for the provision of the service, availability of the necessary equipment);
- Reliability (execution of the order at the agreed time, ensuring the safety of personal data, reliability of financial procedures, safety of cargo during physical distribution);
- Responsibility (ability to fulfill obligations, quality assurance);
- Safety (the organization's ability to ensure the safety of life, health, and property of the client);
- Politeness and communication skills (goodwill, politeness of staff, ability to correctly resolve conflicts).

The consumer draws conclusions regarding the quality of service based on communications, personal preferences and needs, and experience. Thus, the level of quality is a subjective value and depends on the consumer's perception of certain factors [4]. To influence the assessment of quality, it is necessary to segment the consumer market, i.e., divide it into specific groups of consumers according to various criteria, and seek an approach to each group based on the most significant criteria and characteristics of consumption.

Segmentation of the consumer market can be carried out according to geographical criteria, the nature of the service, the type of service or any other criterion. The selection of services that are significant for buyers, their ranking, and the determination of service standards can be done by conducting various surveys and carrying out ongoing monitoring. The organization's resources and capabilities are concentrated in providing customers with the identified services that are most important to them [5]. Each group of products will have its own indicators of service quality and their significance.

By paying attention to research into consumer needs, you can bring your customer service policy as close as possible to the required quality parameters. Nevertheless, at the same time, there is a problem of increasing costs of servicing consumers. The company's management needs to find a level of service at

which the level of costs will not increase significantly. This is one of the problems with setting service boundaries. After all, not every company can afford to spend a significant portion of its profits on serving consumers. Providing high-quality logistics services is the activity of an organization to provide services that best meet the level of consumer requirements [6].

In a methodological sense, the main difficulty in monitoring the quality of the service provision process lies in the fact that the consumption of the service occurs at the time of its provision. For logistics optimization of a service, it is necessary to assess the quality of services using a system of indicators ranked according to their importance for consumers, and to minimize negative discrepancies between what consumers expect and the actual values of service quality indicators.

The improvement and development of service logistics can be considered as optimizing the process of product distribution and improving the quality of service. After all, if there are several suppliers of goods of the same quality on the market, the consumer will give preference to the one that is able to provide a higher level of service during the order fulfillment process. Therefore, the organization must not only maintain the established level of service, but in the process of constantly changing external conditions, develop and improve it [4].

This requires constant monitoring of external environmental factors, competitors and own resources, control of service quality, customer satisfaction and order fulfillment. The management of the organization must set for employees a certain set of goals in the field of quality control, such as accurate implementation of all aspects of customer orders, compliance with delivery times, continuous monitoring of the requirements for the logistics service system, optimization of costs for maintaining the level of logistics service. To achieve this, the organization needs to analyze and streamline its logistics system. Creating an effective logistics system involves the interaction of the organization's employees to ensure the quality of the services provided. If employees in one department of the organization do not perform their tasks well, efforts in other departments will be in vain [5]. Therefore, it is necessary to coordinate and harmonize the activities of the organization's employees involved in fulfilling customer orders.

So, service is inextricably linked with the sales process and represents a set of services provided in the process of ordering, delivery of purchases and further servicing of products. Planning a logistics service is an important stage in increasing the competitiveness of an organization. One of the most difficult issues in service logistics is determining the quality of services. In a methodological sense, the main difficulty in monitoring the quality of the service provision process lies in the fact that the consumption of the service occurs at the time of its provision. For logistics optimization of a service, it is necessary to accurately assess the quality of services using a system of indicators ranked according to their importance for consumers and minimize negative discrepancies between what consumers expect and the actual values of service quality indicators.

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